

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Crabs as pests of wetland rice

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Crabs, a noninsect invertebrate pest of wetland rice, cause much damage in West Bengal. The peak season of their activity is generally from July to October. Two species of freshwater crabs have been identified: *Paratelphusa hydrodromus* Herbst. and *P. spinigera* Wood-Mason (family Potamidae). Their presence in fields is indicated by burrows with mud rims around the opening.

The crabs are mainly carnivorous, but they also feed on rice nursery seedlings

and newly planted ones. They cut at the basal regions of both tender seedlings and older plants. The nocturnal pests often carry young seedlings back to their burrow. Heavily infested rice fields may suffer 60–80% seedling loss. The crabs' burrows also cause leaks in bunds and irrigation systems. ■

Snails — a new pest of azolla

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A snail was found to damage plants of the water fern *Azolla pinnata*, which

harbors the blue-green alga *Anabaena azollae*, during an attempt at its large-scale multiplication for application in rice fields. The snail, identified as *Lymnaea (Pseudosuccinea) luteola* Lamarck, is quite common in West Bengal wetland rice fields. Conchlike in appearance, its average weight is 0.3 g. The snail floats in water and adheres to the lower surface of the free-floating azolla. About 800 snails/m² were observed in a heavily infested rice field. The snails feed voraciously on the host, leaving no remnants. Their peak period of activity is from July to October. The snail is not noticed in the field during the dry winter months from November to January. ■

Soil and crop management

Residual effect of azolla application on rice yield

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Field trials on different manuring rates of azolla, both incorporated and unincorporated, suggest that 10 t of incorporated azolla/ha increases rice yields by about 40% over the untreated control and is comparable to the application of 40 kg N/ha as ammonium sulfate. To study the residual effect of that treatment used in three subsequent seasons, the rice variety Vani was again transplanted in the 1978 wet season in the respective plots.

Tillering in azolla-incorporation treatments was superior to that in the other treatments. Residues of 5, 10, 15, and 20 t of incorporated azolla/ha increased yields by 7.7%, 23.8%, 24.5% and 40.1%, respectively, over the control (see table). Inorganic nitrogen fertilizer treatments of 20, 40, and 80 kg N/ha increased yields by 12.0%, 14.3%, and

Residual fertility effect of azolla and inorganic nitrogen fertilizer on rice yields (variety, Vani).

Treatment ^a	Organic carbon in soil (%) at 1978 dry-season harvest	Yields, 1978 wet season			
		Grain ^b		Straw ^c	
		t/ha	% over control	t/ha	% over control
Control	0.61	1.9	—	1.6	—
5 t azolla inc./ha	0.63	2.0	7.7	1.8	7.4
10 t azolla inc./ha	0.76	2.3	23.8	1.8	6.0
15 t azolla inc./ha	0.73	2.4	24.5	1.8	7.4
20 t azolla inc./ha	0.85	2.7	40.1	1.8	9.0
20 kg N/ha	0.67	2.1	12.0	1.7	4.5
40 kg N/ha	0.66	2.2	14.3	1.8	9.0
60 kg N/ha	0.66	2.1	11.5	1.7	3.0
80 kg N/ha	0.63	2.2	13.8	1.7	4.5
20 kg N + 5 t azolla inc./ha	0.68	2.2	18.0	1.8	6.0
30 kg N + 7.5 t azolla inc./ha	0.76	2.2	18.6	1.9	11.8
40 kg N + 10 t azolla inc./ha	0.86	2.0	7.6	1.8	8.9
3 t azolla uninc.	0.69	2.0	4.3	1.9	14.8
4.5 t azolla uninc.	0.73	1.3	2.3	2.1	29.5
6 t azolla uninc.	0.76	2.1	10.3	2.3	40.2

^ainc. = incorporated, uninc. = unincorporated. ^bAt 14% moisture. ^cSun-dried.

13.8%, respectively. Treatments of azolla incorporated with nitrogen and azolla unincorporated gave higher yields than the control, but less than yields from only incorporated azolla. The straw yield of the azolla incorporated

treatment was almost similar to that of the nitrogen treatment; the straw yield of the azolla-unincorporated treatment was significantly higher than that of all other treatments.

Although the organic carbon content

in the soil of the incorporated azolla and azolla incorporated with nitrogen treatment was almost the same before the residuals study, the azolla-incorporated treatment yielded higher. ■

Azolla manuring and grain yield of rice

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Azolla at 10, 20, and 30 t/ha tested at this station gave significant increase in grain yield. To determine the response of the highest level of azolla that would give a significant yield increase, a replicated trial was conducted during 1979 thaladi season. Azolla at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 t/ha was applied in the plots, and incorporated.

Data on grain yield of rice. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Azolla manure (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	3.9
10	4.4
20	5.0
30	5.6
40	6.2
50	6.7
60	7.3
70	7.6
80	7.8
90	8.0
100	8.0
C.D. = ($P = 0.05\%$)	465

A week later, the short-duration variety ADT31 was planted. Data on grain yield are in the table.

Yield increases in the short-duration ADT31 were significant up to 60 t azolla/ha. ■

Clay mineralogies and available phosphorus and exchangeable potassium status of some Philippine rice soils

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Clay fractions of 160 surface soil samples from 12 major rice-growing provinces in

Table 1. Clay mineralogy in relation to exchangeable potassium in Philippine soils. IRRI, 1980.^a

Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	Dominant minerals	Major minerals	Minor minerals
< 0.1	Vermiculite, beidellite	—	Occasional halloysite
0.1–0.2	Vermiculite, beidellite	—	Montmorillonite
0.2–0.5	Montmorillonite, halloysite, x-ray amorphous material	Montmorillonite, halloysite, x-ray amorphous material	—
> 0.5	Montmorillonite	Hydrous mica	Feldspars

^aDominant = > 50%, major = 20–50%, minor = < 20%, — = not observed.

Table 2. Clay mineralogy in relation to available phosphorus in Philippine rice soils. IRRI, 1980.

Olsen P (ppm)	Dominant/major minerals ^a	Minor minerals
< 5	Halloysite/kaolinite/x-ray amorphous material	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite
5–10	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite	Halloysite/kaolinite/x-ray amorphous material
> 10	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite	Hydrous mica/feldspars

^aDominant = >50%, major = 20–50%, minor = <20%.

the Philippines were analyzed by x-ray diffractometry. The dominant compositions were vermiculite, beidellite, montmorillonite; all three minerals with and without halloysite; halloysite; and x-ray amorphous materials.

In all soils with dominant vermiculite or beidellite, the exchangeable potassium content was less than 0.1 meq/100 g; when those 2 minerals were accompanied by montmorillonite as a minor component, the exchangeable potassium value rose to 0.2 meq/100 g. In almost all other soils the exchangeable potassium content exceeded 0.2 meq/100 g, reflecting an adequate level of available potassium (Table 1).

All soils containing halloysite or x-ray amorphous material had (Olsen) available phosphorus values below 10 ppm, indicating an inadequate available phosphorus status. The mean for samples with dominant halloysite was 2 ppm; the mean for samples with x-ray amorphous material or with halloysite as a secondary component was about 5 ppm. Olsen phosphorus values for almost all other soils containing dominant beidellite, vermiculite, or montmorillonite ranged from 10 to 50 ppm (Table 2), showing a high available phosphorus status.

Farmers' experience and trials by the

Philippine Bureau of Soils showed severe potassium deficiency and lack of response to potassium fertilizers on many soils in Zambales, Pampanga, Tarlac, and Nueva Ecija Provinces, in which vermiculite and beidellite were dominant. Phosphorus deficiency appeared related to the presence of halloysite or x-ray amorphous material in the clay fraction. Soils in which montmorillonite is dominant apparently have adequate supplies of both available phosphorus and potassium.

Because soils with dominant vermiculite and beidellite clay mineralogies fix potassium and ammonium fertilizers and those with dominant halloysite and x-ray amorphous material may inactivate phosphate fertilizers, fertilizer management practices suited to such soils should be developed. ■

Development of semidwarf dryland rice cultivars tolerant of iron chlorosis

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In Maharashtra State, the high yielding semidwarf varieties such as IR8, TN1, Jaya, and their progeny are traditionally